
Interpretative processes and meaning construction in virtual communicative space

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Annotation

This article analyzes the specific features of interpretive processes and the main principles of meaning construction in virtual communication spaces through a systematic analysis of survey results. The study focuses on how meaning is formed from a pragmatic perspective in digital communicative environments, emphasizing the important role of context, participant-related factors, and multimodal media in the interpretation of communicative units. Particular attention is paid to the dynamic and constructive nature of meaning, emphasizing that meaning is not fixed or static, but is constantly formed and transformed in the course of discourse. The study explores how virtual interactions shape understanding through linguistic, social, and technological dimensions. The empirical part of the article is based on survey results that represent diverse interpretations of speech units in virtual communication, demonstrating how pragmatic factors contribute to meaning-making processes. By exploring these mechanisms, the research provides a deeper understanding of how individuals negotiate, interpret, and construct meaning in technologically mediated spaces. The findings contribute to broader discussions in pragmatics, discourse analysis, and virtual communication studies by offering a clearer understanding of communication practices in contemporary digital contexts.

Keywords

Discourse, interpretive process, meaning construction, virtual communicative space, pragmatics, context

Interpretativ jarayonlar va virtual kommunikativ makonda ma'no qurilishi

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada so'rov natijalarini tizimli tahlil qilish orqali virtual aloqa makonlarida talqin jarayonlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va asosiy ma'no qurish

tamoyillari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot raqamli kommunikativ muhitda ma'no pragmatik nuqtai nazardan qanday shakllantirilishiga qaratilgan bo'lib, kommunikativ birliklarni talqin qilishda kontekst, ishtirokchi bilan bog'liq omillar va multimodal vositalarning muhim rolini ta'kidlaydi. Ma'no qat'iy yoki statik emas, balki munozarada doimiy ravishda shakllanib va o'zgarishini ta'kidlab, ma'noning dinamik va konstruktiv tabiatiga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Tadqiqotda virtual o'zaro ta'sirlar tushunishni lingvistik, ijtimoiy va texnologik o'lchovlar orqali qanday shakllantirishi o'rganiladi. Maqolaning empirik qismi virtual muloqotda nutq birliklarining xilma-xil talqinlarini ifodalovchi so'rov natijalariga asoslangan bo'lib, ular pragmatik omillar ma'no yaratish jarayonlariga qanday hissa qo'shishini namoyish etadi. Ushbu mexanizmlarni o'rganish orqali tadqiqot shaxslarning texnologik vositachilik qilingan makonlarda qanday qilib muzokara olib borishi, talqin qilishi va ma'no qurishi haqida chuqurroq tushuncha beradi. Topilgan ma'lumotlar zamonaviy raqamli kontekstlarda aloqa amaliyotini aniqroq tushunishni taklif qilish orqali pragmatika, munozara tahlili va virtual kommunikatsiya tadqiqotlaridagi kengroq muhokamalarga hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar *Diskurs, interpretativ jarayon, ma'no konstruksiyasi, virtual kommunikativ makon, pragmatika, kontekst*

Интерпретационные процессы и смысловое конструирование в виртуальном коммуникативном пространстве

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Аннотация *В данной статье анализируются отличительные особенности интерпретативных процессов и принципы построения смысла в виртуальных коммуникационных пространствах на основе систематического анализа результатов опроса. Исследование фокусируется на том, как смысл конструируется в цифровых коммуникативных средах с прагматической точки зрения, подчеркивая решающую роль контекста, факторов, связанных с участниками, и мультимодальных инструментов в интерпретации коммуникативных единиц. Особое внимание уделяется динамическому и конструктивному характеру смысла, подчеркивая, что смысл не является фиксированным или статичным, а непрерывно формируется и трансформируется в рамках дискурса. Исследование изучает, как виртуальные взаимодействия*

формируют понимание посредством лингвистических, социальных и технологических измерений. Эмпирическая часть статьи основана на результатах опроса, которые отражают разнообразные интерпретации речевых единиц в виртуальной коммуникации, а также демонстрируют, как прагматические факторы способствуют процессам смыслообразования. Изучая эти механизмы, исследование дает более глубокое понимание того, как люди согласовывают, интерпретируют и конструируют смысл в технологически опосредованных пространствах. Полученные результаты вносят вклад в более широкие дискуссии в области прагматики, дискурс-анализа и исследований виртуальной коммуникации, предлагая более четкое понимание коммуникативной практики в современных цифровых контекстах.

Ключевые слова *Дискурс, интерпретативный процесс, конструирование смысла, виртуальное коммуникативное пространство, прагматика, контекст*

Introduction

Nowadays, since the swift improvement of modern technologies, communication strategies has changed the way of how people interact with each other in a daily life, because the appearance of virtual communication and its different features are making the interaction more attractive day-by-day by increasing the usage of integration of text with images, videos, audio and multimedia elements. In that case, meaning construction cannot be simply represented, the meaning is actively constructed and transmitted by users of digital communication platforms together with the connection of linguistic and non-linguistic resources. This situation challenges the classical models of communication requiring scholars to investigate the context, pragmatics and discourse and the implementation of these phenomena in virtual communicative space.

Traditional theoretical models that was created by J.L. Austin (1962), (speech act theory, J.L. Searle (1969), reformulated version of speech acts) and H.P. Grice (1975), conversational principle theory remain highly relevant, but these models should be implemented the virtual communicative sphere. As a result, if it is implemented, there

can be many interpretations of meaning construction.

The concept of meaning construction in virtual communicative space extends beyond individual utterances. In online interaction, messages are integrated with dynamic network of social norms, cultural expectations, platform related conventions, which effects the interpretation. This connection underlines the important features of combination of pragmatic, cognitive, discourse analysis in virtual space. The fully-explained insights about meaning construction and its interpretation in various communication spheres should be systematically investigated and divided into particular terminologies that connected with virtual communicative spaces.

A systematic-linguistic examination demonstrates significant processes how to construct meaning, and formulate speech acts in virtual communicative space. While the availability of abundant studies about meaning and discourse, speech events, that is still novel topic that studying the interpretative processes and speech events to the virtual communication. This research addresses a salient issue: meaning construction in different speech acts and their ways of

interpretation, especially, in online communicative sphere.

Literature review

Theoretical foundations of discourse, meaning construction and interpretative processes are deeply rooted in pragmatics, discourse analysis and cognitive linguistics. The notion of discourse is one of the most salient issues in the sphere of modern linguistics, it investigates how to represent the language units in communicative process. Discourse can be defined in different ways. T. Dijk explained this notion as communicative event which occurs in the combination of language, mind and social context. N.D. Arutyunova clarified the term of discourse as a coherent text in conjunction with basically extralinguistic-pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological, and other factors as well as it is described as a text taken in its episodic aspect or speech that can be regarded as a purposeful social action (Arutyunova, 1990).

According to N. Fairclough, a text can be defined as "a piece of written language – either a complete work like a poem or a novel, or a comparatively distinct component of a work like a chapter. Due to discourse analysis, a slightly broader view has become popular in which a text might be either written or spoken discourse, such that the words used in a discussion (or their written transcription) make up a text. He identified the tendencies of spoken and written discourse in media texts and newspapers. The term of "discourse representation" was used instead of "speech reporting" by N. Fairclough in order to represent the reasons of "writing, as well as speech, may be represented and rather than a transparent report of what was said or written, there is always a decision to interpret and represent it in one way rather than another" (Fairclough, 1995; 54).

It is highly necessary to mention his approach to discourse that Volosinov's classification, primary discourse (the representing and reporting discourse) and secondary discourse (the discourse

represented and reported), can be the basic foundation of Fairclough's discourse representation typology. N. Fairclough incorporated five parameters of texts and discourse types such as modes, boundary maintenance, stylisticity, situationality and setting in comparison with discourse representation. *He explained every parameter with relevant examples and divisions* (Fairclough, 1995; 55).

1. **Mode:** this distinguished between several reporting forms, most notably direct and indirect conversation. Furthermore, it encompassed the type of conversation seen in newspaper headlines, for instance, when secondary discourse is embedded inside primary discourse without being explicitly recognized as such.
2. **Boundary maintenance:** this variable regulates whether the voices of the primary discourse (the reporter) and the secondary discourse (the person being reported) ought to be mixed or separated. There are two kinds of boundary maintenance: a) incorporation, which happens when vocabulary changes translate the secondary discourse into the voice of the main discourse, and b) dissemination, which happens when the voice of the secondary discourse "takes over" the main discourse and alters its linguistic features.
3. **Stylistism:** This evaluates how well the non-ideational, interpersonal meanings of the secondary discourse (like the exact way something was said) are represented. The sources assert that focusing on the content of the speech rather than its stylistic quality often leads to very low media coverage.
4. **Context:** This discusses how much the study captures the setting in which the secondary discourse occurred.
5. **Environment:** This emphasizes how the reader or listener interprets the secondary material is impacted by the

surrounding text. Setting devices are often used to predispose a certain interpretation, such as using the word "warned" to represent the illocutionary force of the statement" (Fairclough, 1995).

These parameters collectively help to identify tendencies in media representation, such as low demarcation between voices and a heavy focus on the ideational meaning (the "what") rather than the interpersonal context (the "how" and "where") of the original discourse".

Another important aspect of this research is meaning construction and its interpretation. S. Levinson described as a two-stage affair in some philosophical approaches: the meaning of the utterance is a function from contexts to propositions, which are then used to determine truth values. This means pragmatics is often logically prior to semantics, because it fixes the proposition that a sentence expresses on a specific occasion. He explained that the central concept in meaning construction is the discrepancy between what is literally said and what the speaker intended to communicate (Levinson, 1983; 23). The notion of implicature is used to explain how listeners work out what parts of a message are effectively conveyed even when they are not explicitly stated. According to the writer, context is not just a physical setting, it includes participants' beliefs and assumptions about temporal, spatial, and social settings, as well as the state of the knowledge of those participating in the interaction. Moreover, interpretation of any context involves distinguishing between "figure" (the main point of what is said) and the "ground" (background assumptions/presuppositions). Presuppositions provide the ground against which the main import of an utterance is assessed. (Levinson, 1993; 97).

According to M. Bakhtin "speech genres are boundless, because the various possibilities of human activity are inexhaustible, and because each sphere of activity contains an entire repertoire of speech genres that

differentiate and grow as the particular sphere that develops and becomes more complex. Special emphasis should be placed on the extreme heterogeneity of speech genres (oral or written)" (Bakhtin, 1986; 60). However, J. Searle analyzed the speech situations by dividing and reformulating speech acts theory. He explained the reason why he studied speech acts as all linguistic communication involves linguistic acts (Searle, 1969).

One of the main topical issues of this research is communication and its representation in digital discourse. V. Karasik defined the notion of communication as the main goal of interaction is to maintain the unity of man and society, the dialectal overcoming and confirmation of the individual's separateness (Karasik, 2002; 284). Moreover, N. Fairclough also stated that "interactional norms involving aspects of the interpersonal meaning and forms (for example, turn-taking systems) may be ideological assumptions about social relations underlying interactional practices such as politeness strategies" (1995; 23). Especially, "much of what goes under the name of pragmatic analysis lies on the borderline text and discourse practice" (1995; 134). "Communication is a subjective-objectifying, external norm or the flow of language activity, a phenomenon or language activity, a way of being of the language world, a sphere of expressive-communicative functioning" (Atayan, 1982; 31).

"Any speech activity aims to influence the communicants in the conditions of communication and to achieve a certain result, effect, success, motivated by both practical expediency and the intention of the communicants. The effect of such an impact, of course, depends on the choice of the most appropriate means in a particular situation and the optimal language solution for a particular communicative task" (Stepanov, 1981; 325).

"As is known, speech formation first goes through the stage of cognitive activity, that is, in the process of inner (internal) speech, model patterns of the future speech structure are

formed. Such patterns can be of various types. The task of the speaker is to choose one of these patterns. The selection is controlled by the rules that activate within the framework of interpersonal relations. The set of speech structures that are present in the speaker's mind and allow him to achieve the intended communicative goal is the pragmatic reserve and potential of this person. The choice of the method of expression and expression is also freed or limited depending on the breadth or narrowness of this set. The choice of the method of expression and expression is related to the rules of the rhetoric of the text. Using the possibilities of the existing rhetorical reserve, the speaker transfers the concept that has arisen in thought and has a certain illocutionary content into the text. The realization of the concept in the text of the speech situation is carried out by means of choosing a specific form of expression" (Safarov, 2008; 143).

"Influence through language is carried out not by simple evaluative statements such as: "this is good", "this is bad", but by various language designations that contain a socially determined evaluative component. The use of such designations makes it possible to express assessments implicitly, imperceptibly for the communicants and to evoke in them the appropriate attitude and behavior. This does not mean the impact that the language has and spreads by itself, but the fact that the assessments and views of certain social groups are fixed in different points of view on linguistic use and are subsequently transferred by the language to the special impact of the corresponding social groups" (Matveeva, 1984; 5-6; Kiseleva, 1978, Dridze, 1980).

According to S.V. Pervukhina, M.P. Churikov, using digital technologies, the text may be creolized. They integrate graphic and textual depictions of both connotative and denotative information. The author's worldview is expressed by the choice of memes, images, and emojis, which also allows for the communication of emotions. Written language used on internet sites shares features with

spoken language: It contains errors, pauses, slang words, and spontaneity. Obviously, there is a difference between written internet discourse and the norms of literary language and written speech genres. In the internet sphere, new genres related to the previously stated attributes have emerged, such as blogs, video articles, posts, and channels. Hybrid genres exist in an intermediary stage between spoken and written language (Perxukhina, Churikov, 2021).

N.P. Revyakina defined that the digital technology that has sped up the creation of new words like user, password, device, story, log in, and so on. Since these words typically originate in English, we might talk about how English is becoming more and more integrated into other languages around the world. This phenomenon is known as "globanglization" (Revyakina, 2013; 92).

E.V. Murugova, T.A. Lopatukhina stated that the internet is a global network, so you can talk to anyone who has a website. Social media lets you share your experiences with professionals that run blogs and teach courses (called "marathons"). The epidemic has given rise to a new kind of internet corporate events complete with rules and customs of their own. Using photoshop and PR techniques, the volume of deliberately false content (fake information, stuffing) being produced is rising. The idea of "digital literacy" is introduced; it comprises the ability to utilize contemporary devices and technology. The notion of "experience of identifying manipulations in the digital world" is vital, in our opinion (Murugova, Lopatuxina, 2012).

According to Crystal "the Internet consists of computer networks that have universal criteria letting messages go from anywhere. A registered computer (or host) can be connected to any host on any network. Originally developed in the 1960s in the United States as an experiment, the network swiftly grew to encompass military, regional, and federal organizations users of companies, universities, and private people. Right now, it is

the most popular worldwide. with over 300 million connected hosts, the largest computer network by 2005, expanding the range of services provided as well as permitting an unprecedented amount of people to interact by email, discussion forums, and the accessibility of digital "pages" addressing any topic". Moreover, chat group discussion is nonstop and focused on one topic. organised into "rooms" at particular websites, each with a computer. Those who are interested might participate in the discussion. The interaction might happen based on the local conditions in real time (synchronous) or later (asynchronous) (Crystal, 2006).

"An instant messaging service allows electronic conversations between people who know each other to take place in real time. It therefore differs from e-mail messaging (where the exchanges are asynchronous) and from chatgroups (where the participants are usually numerous and unknown to each other). There are now a number of systems, such as MSN Messenger, ICQ, AOL Instant Messenger, and Yahoo! Messenger, displaying broadly similar properties. Typically, the participants see each unit of text as soon as it is typed (and sent), and are alerted to whether someone is typing a contribution" (Crystal, 2006).

Ch. Durscheid and C. Frehner wrote a handbook about "the pragmatics of computer mediated communication" and stated that we sent millions of emails in our daily life communication, email has become a common type of interaction which is used by the young and old. The stated that comparing to other ways of communication in computer mediated discourse, email can be regarded as an old mode which is losing popularity as new, competing modes have sprung up. But email is still the most important since it is the only CMC program available which the average Internet user is familiar with. So, when filling out forms, for example, The email address of the person is sought; not their Skype user ID or a Twitter account, a habit that is probably going to persist for some time. Emails are utilized here

for a range of purposes, including sending greetings and invitations, exchanging information to send digital data (ranging from simple word) or a URL across the internet from videos and photos to documents). It is a little less personal than a letter and also a subtle method of contact that also appeals to those who would not otherwise engage (Durscheid, Frehner, 2013).

Ch. Durscheid (2020; 63) "The word "emoji" comes from Japanese; it stands for the combination of "picture" (e) and "character" (moji), and the phonetic resemblance to the word "emoticon" is purely coincidental. In Japan, the history of emojis dates back to the last century. Shigetaka Kurita is considered their inventor; in the late 1990s, he designed small black-and-white graphics for what was then Japan's largest mobile phone provider, which could be used to supplement text. The success story of emojis thus began in Japan. This also explains why the meanings of many emojis are rooted in Japanese culture. For example, the dog poop emoji is used in Japan when you want to wish someone good luck; but in general, in other cultures, it serves to represent something negative or to critically comment on someone else's statement" (Durscheid, 2020; 63).

According to research by E. Dresner and S. Herring, the concept of "emoticons" (emotion and icons) is important in the analysis of digital communication. This concept was introduced by Scott Falman, a computer scientist at Carnegie Mellon University, and refers to a "smiling face" or graphic symbol in connection with computer-mediated communication (CMC). Therefore, today, with the development of modern technologies and the improvement of communication methods, the study of emoticons and their classification into categories, speech units and speech acts in computer-mediated communication becomes one of the promising areas in modern linguistics (Dresner and Herring, 2020).

The construction of meaning in virtual environments is examined as a process of

modifying conventional linguistic norms to the distinctive limitations and potential of the electronic medium that can be regarded as NETSPEAK by D. Crystal (2006). This medium is a "linguistic revolution" that is neither pure speech nor pure writing, but a "third medium" (or even a "fourth medium" when including sign language) with its own rules for creating meaning.

According to Crystal, D. (2006), one of the primary challenges in virtual meaning construction is the absence of facial expressions, gestures and vocal nuances which characterize face-to-face interaction. To develop these stages, users have developed different strategies:

Emoticons/Smileys: these keyboard combinations serve as a "crude" but helpful way to signal emotional intent, forestalling gross misperceptions of a speaker's meaning.

Verbal glosses: meaning is often constructed using angle brackets to describe actions or feelings, such as <grin> or <Henry eyes Jane warily>, which add a narrative layer to the interaction.

Prosodic graphology: users can employ exaggerated spelling (soooo), capitalization for shouting (I SAID NO) and repeated punctuation (!!!) in order to construct "sonic prominence" and emotional intensity in a text-based space.

Moreover, in e-mail and chats, meaning is constructed through "framing"- pasting parts of a previous message into a response. This creates "nested dialogues where replies are interspersed within the original text, a unique feature of digital language that maintains context across time. In chatgroups and virtual worlds, the choice of a nickname can be called as a "ritual act" that establishes an electronic identity and invites specific types of interaction, acting as a "discourse signal" for who is being addressed.

Furthermore, it is important to consider about the role of semantic web that can be regarded as a new stage of meaning construction where information is encoded in a machine-processable form (Crystal, 2006).

Meaning is constructed not just for humans but for computers through metadata (descriptions of documents) and ontologies (formal description of relationships between terms). The goal is a "web of data with meaning", where programs can learn concepts from source data to help humans find and classify information more effectively.

According to Crystal, D., another crucial factor in virtual world communication is social functions and identity that can express meaning social or phatic way rather than purely informational. That means that a lot of users construct meaning by adopting the specific linguistic "dialect" of their group (e.g. using abbreviations or deviant spellings like computer), which serves as a marker of identity and solidarity.

Methodology

This research analyses meaning construction and interpretative processes in virtual communication. Thus, this study used qualitative and quantitative approaches in order to investigate users' perceptions, interpretations and communicative intentions. The data were collected according to the carefully-designed questionnaire consisting of both close-ended and open-ended questions. The special questionnaire had been organized in google forms that based on the effect of emojis, expressions, speech types they use, and common misunderstandings in online communication.

The questionnaire participants consist of selected users of digital communication platforms. Selection criteria includes age, frequency of internet use, and familiarity with digital platforms, providing that participants have enough experience in navigating online discourse. This strategy improves the relevance and reliability of the survey data. During the process of completing the survey, the data collection was conducted anonymously to provide honest and unbiased responses.

The identification of results is based on te main concepts from pragmatics and discourse analysis, speech act theories, implicature and

context dependency as well as the role of multimodal elements such as emojis.

Results

According to the survey results, 16 respondents from selected doctoral students who are aware about the linguistic communication and theories, thus, they expressed their attitudes towards to the open-ended and close-ended questions. According to their responses, telegram is used commonly by the most of users for virtual communication and some of the respondents expressed they spend more than 5 hours for online communication. Representative type of speech acts were selected by participants as the most commonly used speech act and also, the majority of participants regards messages without emojis can be more formal.

Discussion

The findings of this research represents the meaning construction in virtual communication and the role of multimodal elements that are the main tools of online communication. Moreover, the theoretical notions of great linguists and specialists such as Austin, Searle, Bakhtin, Levinson, Fairlough, and Crystal were clearly conducted in order to identify how meaning is constructed and interpreted in virtual communicative space. Moreover, the results of the questionnaire demonstrated the importance of paralinguistic and multimodal elements such as emojis, punctuation markers, in the process of making interpretations.

Respondents expressed that these kinds of elements often can be regarded as pragmatic markers which helps to identify intention, emotion or mitigate ambiguity and misunderstandings. According to the discussion, the meaning construction in virtual communicative space can be regarded as the integration of linguistic, cognitive, and social factors, and also, questionnaire-based method of this research provides important information how users manage such kind of complexity from internal and experiential perspective.

Conclusion

To sum up, the findings demonstrated that virtual communication counts on pragmatic competence including the ability to interpret implicit meanings and also recognize communicative intentions as well as employs multimodal elements effectively. Emojis, punctuation and other non-verbal elements play very important role in compensating for the absence of face-to-face interaction, but their interpretation remains subjective and variable. Although this study has some contributions for the modern linguistics, it has some particular limitations also. The reliance of self-reported data may not fully embrace actual communicative behavior and sample size and composition may limit generalization of results. Future research could expand the number of participants and collaborate cross-cultural comparing together with combining survey data with real discourse analysis for more comprehensive approach.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

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